

Welcome to the 3rd DIGITISE Newsletter!

In this issue, we look back at key recent activities, including the 4th DIGITISE Plenary Meeting held in Murcia and CIRCE's presentation on the role of KPIs at the 5th International Conference on Applied Science and Engineering. You will also find updates from the DIGITISE team at AUSTRALO, UCD and Unparallel, alongside highlights from the E-ENERGY Cluster's activities during Enlit 2025.

As the year comes to a close, we would also like to wish you a restful holiday break and our best wishes for the year ahead.

DIGITISE Team

4th DIGITISE Plenary Meeting in Murcia

The 4th DIGITISE Plenary Meeting took place on 3–4 December 2025 at the Voltiva Energy facility in Murcia, bringing partners together for two days of structured discussion and technical coordination. The consortium reviewed progress up to Month 18, covering overall achievements, management and reporting procedures, and key updates from across the work packages.

[Read the full article](#)

4th Plenary Meeting Recap - DIGITISE Data Model and Data Governance Framework

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#DIGITISEevents

5th International Conference on
**Applied Science and
Engineering**

 June 26-27, 2025

 Amsterdam, Netherlands

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<https://appliedscienceconference.com/>

CIRCE Presented Research on the Role of KPIs at the 5th International Conference on Applied Science and Engineering

CIRCE, one of the members of the DIGITISE consortium, participated in the 5th International Conference on Applied Science and Engineering under the theme “Technological Developments & Modern Trends in Applied Science and Advanced Engineering.”

[Read more](#)

#DIGITISEteam

How to Maximise DIGITISE visibility? - Interview with AUSTRALO - Dissemination Leader

In this interview, we speak with Giulia and Aga from AUSTRALO, who lead the Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation activities in the DIGITISE project. With complementary backgrounds in EU project management, marketing, and strategic communication, they share how they came to collaborate on DIGITISE and their approach to making the project's work visible, engaging, and impactful.

[Read the full interview](#)

Activating Prosumers Through AI - UCD's Role in Advancing Digital Tools for DIGITISE

In this interview, we spoke with Vlasis Koutsos, Research Assistant at University College Dublin (UCD), about the university's contribution to the DIGITISE project. Vlasis shares how UCD's work is supporting energy and well-being literacy through AI-powered tools, promoting more informed and secure household energy use. He also discusses the collaborative efforts within DIGITISE, the expected outcomes, and how their research could inform future policies for a more sustainable and user-driven energy ecosystem in Europe.

[Read the full interview](#)

Guiding Smarter Energy Decisions with Unparallel's Role in Consumer-Focused Innovation

In this interview, we speak with Tiago Teixeira, COO at Unparallel (UNP) about their technical contributions to the DIGITISE project, particularly in empowering consumers to make informed energy decisions. With a clear focus on the household level, Unparallel is responsible for developing the Asset Sizing Application, a tool designed to guide users in choosing energy-efficient investments based on personalised consumption data.

[Read the full article](#)

#E-ENERGYCluster

E-ENERGY Cluster at Enlit Europe 2025

Enlit Europe 2025 took place on 18-20 November in Bilbao, a city that has grown into an important reference point for the global energy sector. Held at the Bilbao Exhibition Centre, the event gathered professionals from across Europe and beyond, providing a setting well suited to discussions on how digitalisation, innovation and regional cooperation are shaping the continent's energy landscape. The [E-ENERGY Cluster](#), bringing together the EU-funded projects **DIGITISE**, **DECODIT**, **ENERGENIUS**, **CELINE** and **EU-DREAM**, took part through a webinar, a booth in the EU Projects Zone and an interactive workshop.

[Read more](#)

Watch the Recap of ENLIT 2025!

LISTEN TO THE EPISODE “The EU Energy Projects Podcast: The E-Nergy Cluster in action – insights from DECODIT and ENERGENIUS”

[Read more](#)

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